

Antibacterial coating of substrates based on cationic biocides-enhanced thin films of selected polystyrene-based copolymers

Kateřina Hamalova^{a,*}, Viktorie Neubertova^a, Adela Jagerova^b, Anna Kutova^c,
Jan Novotny^d, Zdeňka Kolska^a

^a Centre for Nanomaterials and Biotechnology, Faculty of Science, Jan Evangelista Purkyne University in Ustı nad Labem, Pasteurova 15, 400 96, Ustı nad Labem, Czech Republic

^b Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, Jan Evangelista Purkyne University in Ustı nad Labem, Pasteurova 15, 400 96, Ustı nad Labem, Czech Republic

^c Department of Solid State Engineering, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology, Technicka 5, 166 28, Prague, Czech Republic

^d Institute of Technology and Materials, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Jan Evangelista Purkyne University in Ustı nad Labem, Pasteurova 7, 400 96, Ustı nad Labem, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Block copolymers
Thin films
Coatings
Cationic biocides
Antibacterial surfaces
Antibacterial activity

ABSTRACT

Developing antimicrobial coatings is an important challenge nowadays, significant for managing microbial contamination across various applications, including medical devices, food packaging, and waste management. This study examines the preparation, modification and characterization of specific polystyrene-block-polyisoprene-block-polystyrene (SIS) and polystyrene-block-polybutadiene-block-polystyrene (SBS) thin polymer films modified by selected cationic biocides (CB), namely chlorhexidine (CHX) and dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide (DTAB). Two approaches were used to prepare and modify polymer films. First, CBs were added directly to the polymer solution. Second, pristine samples were exposed to plasma or UV radiation and afterwards immersed in an ethanol solution of CBs. Morphology, chemical structure and surface properties of the samples were characterized. Furthermore, their stability was evaluated, with a focus on their antibacterial activity and adhesion to selected substrates. The antibacterial activity of films improved when modified with CHX, as demonstrated by testing against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Specifically, one of the CHX-modified samples resulted in a bacterial survival rate of only 0.2 % in comparison with the control, less than the survival rates observed in DTAB-modified samples. Surface characterization revealed that lower zeta potential and contact angle values exhibited a correlation with higher hydrophilicity and antimicrobial activity, especially for CHX-modified films. Particularly the effect of surface charge is significant and plays a vital role. This work demonstrates several positive results of incorporating antibacterial agents into a polymer matrix. It also provides new insights into these materials as potential antibacterial coatings for a wide range of applications.

1. Introduction

Antimicrobial polymeric materials and surfaces are popular research topics due to their importance in many areas, including medical devices, food packaging, agriculture, aquaculture, and prevention of marine biofouling [1–4]. Extensively studied, many polymeric composites containing quaternary ammonium groups are exceptionally effective antimicrobial polymers, showing a meaningful ability to kill microbes [5–8]. Bacterial biofilms that form on surfaces have a significant impact on infection-related health. The immediate need to solve this problem requires coatings that either prevent some biofilm formation or

eliminate some of the existing biofilms. Effective antimicrobial coatings prevent some bacterial attachment and kill many germs on contact, both before and after surfaces are touched [9–12]. Many antimicrobial agents adhere to the cell surface because their reactive functional groups interact with some of the microorganisms' extracellular polymeric substances. Several complex mechanisms are activated immediately after secure attachment. This involves disrupting some cell membrane architecture, and it also suppresses several protein synthesis or metabolic pathways, interfering with some nucleic acid synthesis [13]. The important negative charge on the surface of many microbial cells makes cationic antimicrobials their most likely binding partners. This class

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: katerina.hamalova@ujep.cz (K. Hamalova).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2025.109020>

Received 9 June 2025; Received in revised form 20 October 2025; Accepted 27 October 2025

Available online 28 October 2025

0142-9418/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

contains some quaternary ammonium compounds. Cationic chemicals in some disinfectants function through electrostatic attraction, penetration and diffusion [12,13].

Cationic biocides, including quaternary ammonium salts (QAS), biguanides, and bisbiguanides, have been used for many years in medical applications and daily life as common antiseptics and disinfectants [14]. Cationic biocides include a wide range of chemicals and mixtures. Their functions include acting as antimicrobials, surfactants, preservatives, antistatic agents, plasticizers and dispersants. Many detergents, hand sanitizers, personal care products and various kinds of wipes (including surface, baby, hand and disinfectant wipes), as well as several pesticides, commonly contain CB. A lot of products, such as personal care items, use polymers, which often include CB. They are also used as antimicrobial coatings on many surfaces, including multiple textiles, a range of biomedical instruments and several high-touch areas in public spaces [4,15–17]. Many CBs, especially QAS, including DTAB, contain a single central ammonium group bearing a permanent positive charge; this group is typically attached to several alkyl and aromatic substituents. The properties of several QAS, such as function, performance, environmental impact and toxicity, are determined by their substituents and alkyl chain length [17,18]. Chlorhexidine is a bisbiguanide antiseptic known for its effectiveness against a broad spectrum of microorganisms. This mechanism works by forming interactions between phospholipids, leading to the displacement of cations like Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} [19–21]. Many polymers can be modified with cationic biocides to increase their ability to kill germs [13]. There are two ways for incorporating antibacterial compounds: chemical and physical. Each has its advantages and disadvantages. When physically bound to a matrix, antibacterial compounds are gradually released into the environment until the antimicrobial system leaches them out, lowering their concentration. On the other hand, biocide moieties that are chemically bound to polymer chains by antibacterial agents form a permanent biological barrier, preventing microorganisms from interacting with the matrix. This approach provides a much larger surface area, increasing interaction with pathogens [13].

Our motivation for this research was to create polymeric films from block copolymers with the addition of specific antibacterial agents in their structure or subsequently modify them with specific techniques to study their potential as antibacterial coatings. One of the main goals of this study was to prepare the samples in the easiest way, such as the solution casting method. This study investigates the preparation, characterization, and analysis of two types of thin polymer films modified with two antibacterial compounds via two different methods. These films have been characterized intensively, and in particular, their antimicrobial activity has been studied. These films were deposited onto different substrates (glass, aluminium, and steel), and their adhesion strength was tested. As far as is currently known, this research is one of the first to demonstrate the potential of styrene-based block copolymers to create polymer films improved by cationic biocides as antibacterial coatings for important applications such as plastic, metal, and glass waste containers, as well as medical instruments.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Polystyrene-block-polyisoprene-block-polystyrene (SIS, styrene wt. 22 %) and polystyrene-block-polybutadiene-block-polystyrene (SBS, styrene wt. 30 %) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Burlington, USA). Cyclohexane (C_6H_{12}) and chloroform ($CHCl_3$, stabilized with amylene) were provided by Lach-Ner, s.r.o. (Neratovice, Czech Republic). Chlorhexidine 98 % and dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide 99 % were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, USA). Luria Bertani medium (LB, Sigma Aldrich), plate count agar (PCA, Oxoid), phosphate buffered saline (PBS, prepared with concentrations of NaCl at 136.8 mol/m^3 , KCl at 2.68 mol/m^3 , Lachner (Neratovice, Czech

Republic), $Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 12 H_2O$ at 7.96 mol/m^3 and KH_2PO_4 at 1.47 mol/m^3 , Penta (Praha, Czech Republic), with pH adjusted to 7.4), *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*, DBM 3138, collection of Molecular biology laboratory at the Institute of biochemistry at UCT Prague), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*, CCM 4516, collection of Molecular biology laboratory at the Institute of biochemistry at UCT Prague).

2.2. Polymer films preparation and modification

SIS and SBS polymer films were prepared by dissolving 18.21 g of polystyrene-block-polyisoprene-block-polystyrene (SIS) in 164 mL of chloroform and 18.23 g of polystyrene-block-polybutadiene-block-polystyrene (SBS) in 164 mL of cyclohexane with continuous stirring at 280 rpm for 2 h. The mixtures were then heated to $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and stirred until the polymers were all dissolved, creating a clear solution. Additionally, polymer films were modified with two antibacterial compounds, specifically (a) chlorhexidine (CHX) and (b) dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide (DTAB) of two different concentrations: 0.5 % wt. and 1.5 % wt. In the first preparation method, the desired amount of CB (0.5 % wt.: 0.2 mL; 1.5 % wt.: 0.6 mL) was added directly to the polymer solutions, and the solutions were then stirred at 250 rpm for 30 min at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. 14 mL of the heated solutions were poured into Petri dishes, and the samples were left in a fume hood for several days. The samples were then taken from the Petri dishes and washed with distilled water. In the second preparation method, pristine polymer samples were prepared and then exposed to plasma (PA) for 10 min or UV light (254 nm UV) for 30 min before being soaked in an ethanol solution of CHX and DTAB (0.5 % and 1.5 %) for a few hours. The samples were removed from the modification solutions and thoroughly washed with distilled water to eliminate any remaining residue. Fig. 1a shows the sample preparation technique.

Thin polymer films of SIS and SBS were prepared for cross-cut testing using a film casting knife with an adjustable gap clearance ranging from 0 to $3800 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ (BYK-Gardner GmbH, Geretsried, Germany). The films were prepared using the same two methods as before. Aluminium, steel, and glass plates were positioned on a drawdown plate and secured with a clip. A casting knife, adjusted with a gap clearance of $150 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, was used to cast 3 mL of dissolved SIS and SBS polymer on each plate. The sample preparation procedure is shown in Fig. 1b.

2.3. Polymer films characterization

Surface properties and morphology of prepared polymer films were characterized by available techniques. As well, antimicrobial tests were performed, and samples were also subjected to cross-cut tests. Measurements of water uptake, swelling ratios and assessment of samples ageing were made to characterize the properties of the polymeric films, with a focus on their stability in the presence of water. A detailed description of these methods is provided in the Supplementary Material, in section 1. Sample characterization.

2.3.1. Zeta potential determination

The surface charge was determined by the electrokinetic analyses (zeta potential determination) for all samples using the SurPASS 3 Instrument (Anton Paar, AUT). The samples, placed on two holders ($2 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$), were positioned in the adjustable gap cell with a $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ gap height in contact with a 1 mol/m^3 KCl electrolyte solution in distilled water of pH = 5.5. Zeta potential determinations were performed in three cycles by the streaming current method, showing a relative error of 10 %. Zeta potentials were calculated by the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski (HS) equation.

2.3.2. Contact angle measurement

The static contact angle of distilled water, characteristic of surface wettability, was measured using goniometry with a drop shape analyser DSA30 (KRÜSS GmbH, DE). A drop of water with a specified volume of

Fig. 1. Sample preparation procedure: a) dissolving the polymer and pouring the polymer solution into a Petri dish; b) dissolving the polymer and casting the polymer solution with a casting knife on the selected substrate.

(2.00 ± 0.05) μL was applied to the surface of the films using an automated needle. The images of water drops were then analysed automatically using ADVANCE software. The measurements were performed at room temperature ($20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) ten times with a relative error of 5 %.

2.3.3. Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

The surface morphology was examined using atomic force microscopy (AFM) with an NT-MDT NTEGRA Aura instrument. The AFM measurements were performed in semi-contact mode using silicon probes (resonant frequency of 190 kHz, force constant of 48 N/m). The collected scans were analysed using Gwyddion software (version 2.64) [22].

2.3.4. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were performed using a Nicolet 6700 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) using a ZnSe ATR crystal in the $500\text{--}4.000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The changes in the chemical composition of the prepared thin polymer films, resulting from differing amounts of chlorhexidine as well as different types of post-modifications performed on the samples were detected. OMNIC software was used to analyse FTIR spectra.

2.3.5. Antibacterial activity test

The antibacterial effect of the selected samples was measured using the drop plate method against two bacterial strains: the gram-positive bacteria (G+) *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*; CCM 4516) and the gram-negative bacteria (G-) *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*; CCM 4517). Firstly, the inoculum was prepared using one colony of each bacterial strain into 4 mL (*S. aureus*) or 25 mL (*E. coli*) of Luria-Bertani (LB) liquid medium. Inoculum were incubated overnight on an orbital shaker at $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The next day, they were diluted into phosphate buffered saline (PBS) to a final concentration of approximately $2 \times 10^9\text{ m}^{-3}$ (*S. aureus*) and 1×10^9

m^{-3} (*E. coli*). Then, 100 μL of the bacterial suspension was dropped in pentaplicate on the surface of the samples. After 2 h, three drops (25 μL) from each 100 μL drop were placed onto the plate count agar (PCA, Oxoid). Cultivation took place overnight and the next day, the number of colony-forming units (CFU) was calculated. All the experiments were performed under sterile conditions. The results are presented as an average of 15 values with standard deviation.

3. Results and discussion

In the following section, the various results of characterization techniques used in this study are discussed. The main purpose of these characterizations is to determine the effect of the surface charge determined by zeta potential and surface wettability on the antibacterial properties of the samples. Additionally, we examine how the given modification techniques affect the morphology and stability of the samples. The results of water uptake and swelling ratio analysis, as well as ageing of the samples and cross-cut tests, are presented in Supplementary Material. The DTAB-modified samples did not perform as well as the chlorhexidine (CHX) samples. Therefore, here are primarily presented results for CHX-modified samples with a comparison to the relevant DTAB samples; the rest of the DTAB samples are presented in the Supplementary Material as well.

3.1. Zeta potential determination

The zeta potential indicates the surface charge and chemical properties of the sample surfaces, considerably influencing bacterial interactions. Bacterial adhesion is typically resisted by surfaces with a negative zeta potential because of electrostatic repulsion of cells. Zeta potential determinations show differences between individual samples and especially after individual modification steps. As is clear from Fig. 2,

Fig. 2. Zeta potential of a) SIS and b) SBS polymer films with CHX modifications and plasma (PA) and UV treatments at two different concentrations.

zeta potential values changed more significantly for SBS samples compared with SIS ones. Adding cationic biocides considerably changed the largely negative zeta potential of DTAB-modified samples compared to unmodified samples and those modified with chlorhexidine. CHX treatment of the samples changed the zeta potential to the less negative values in comparison with pristine samples, showing a presence of large amounts of amino groups on the surfaces given by CHX molecules grafted on the surface. These different results corresponded well with the chemical composition of CHX and DTAB. While CHX consists of many amino groups in the molecule, which affect the zeta potential value towards less negative or positive surface charge values, on the other hand, DTAB has only 1 quaternary amino group and a long carbon chain, which has a non-polar character and leads to the negative surface charge.

It is evident that both SIS (Fig. 2a–S2a) and SBS (Fig. 2b–S2b) polymer films have a negative zeta potential due to the presence of non-polar hydrocarbon chain inclusive aromatics. The SBS pristine polymer

film has a zeta potential value of -58.0 mV, while the SIS pristine polymer film has a zeta potential value of -27.0 mV. This difference is caused by the variable presence of styrene, which caused the much negative surface charge. UV and plasma exposure caused the changes in the zeta potential, indicating a decrease in surface polarity. The further incorporation of CHX and DTAB onto the UV- and plasma-activated polymer films leads to an additional change in the zeta potential, suggesting another change in the surface chemistry of the polymer films. The zeta potential and surface polarity may depend on parameters such as the wavelength and exposure time of the UV, the intensity and exposure time of the plasma treatment, and the composition of the polymer film. These factors affect the development of new functional groups on the polymer surface, influencing the zeta potential and other surface characteristics. Also, different concentrations of DTAB and CHX play an important role in the surface chemistry and changes in zeta potential.

Fig. 3. Contact angles of a) SIS and b) SBS polymer films with CHX modifications and plasma (PA) and UV treatments at two different concentrations.

3.2. Surface wettability

Surface wettability, determined by contact angle, can also explain the studied antimicrobial effectiveness. The results of the contact angle measurements on SIS (Fig. 3a, S3a) and SBS (Fig. 3b–S3b) polymers are shown in the graphs below. Hydrophilic surfaces resist some bacterial adhesion because their lower contact angles reduce the surface energy that attracts a certain amount of microbial growth [23–27]. Pristine SIS and SBS polymers are hydrophobic, with contact angles of 96.2° and 93.5° , respectively, because of the non-polar hydrocarbon groups on their surfaces. Surface modification considerably decreased the contact angle for most samples, indicating the presence of polar groups on surfaces, thus improving their hydrophilicity. Plasma and UV treatments, especially those with CHX, were highly effective, likely due to the addition of polar groups at the polymer surface, improving its hydrophilicity. The addition of CHX or DTAB has changed several surface characteristics and the chemical composition of SIS and SBS polymer films, resulting in modifications to the surface wettability. Polymer film composition and the interaction between CB and the polymer matrix determine how CB affects wettability. Surface treatments like SIS + UV + CHX 0.5 % (Fig. 3a), exhibiting the contact angle of 74.7° and SBS + UV + CHX 0.5 % (Fig. 3b), showing a 78.7° contact angle, are important examples. These values indicated a shift toward more hydrophilic surfaces in comparison with unmodified SIS and SBS, and this characteristic is desirable for antimicrobial behaviour. SIS polymer considerably outperformed SBS polymer. Even though the DTAB-modified samples were in most cases less hydrophilic than those modified with CHX, they still had smaller contact angles than the unmodified samples.

3.3. AFM morphology characterization

Only the samples containing 1.5 % chlorhexidine were selected for AFM analysis, as the literature suggests [28–31] that more significant morphological changes can be expected at higher concentrations of the antibacterial agent than at lower concentrations. The tapping-mode AFM was used to study the morphology of the samples. Sphere-like structures can be observed in both polymers, and both polymers also exhibit a certain granular structure, with a pronounced effect observed in the SIS (Figs. 4 and 5) samples. The SBS (Figs. 6 and 7) polymer, on the other hand, is wavier and exhibits higher roughness. SIS samples are generally smoother and more elastic, while SBS samples are denser. The RMS (Root Mean Square) roughness of the samples varied, with samples treated with plasma or UV light exhibiting the highest roughness in both polymers. These treatments resulted in an increase in surface granularity, creating undulations, particularly in the case of SBS. The change in surface morphology may be due to the photodegradation of macromolecules with long chains. These undulations are likely to be caused by the formation of oxygen-containing functional groups resulting from these treatments [32–34]. The results correlate with the FTIR study, which observed the formation of new carbonyl and hydroxyl groups on the surface after UV and plasma exposure. The results of AFM analysis are also consistent with our contact angle measurements, which revealed a decrease in contact angle and an increase in hydrophilicity in samples treated with UV light and plasma. These results agree with those reported in the literature regarding the effect of UV and plasma treatments on polymers [35–37].

3.4. FTIR spectroscopy characterization

FTIR spectroscopy revealed how plasma treatment, UV exposure, or

Fig. 4. AFM 2D images of selected SIS samples, scans of $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$: a) SIS PRISTINE, b) SIS + 1.5 % CHX, c) SIS + UV + 1.5 % CHX and d) SIS + PA + 1.5 % CHX.

Fig. 5. AFM 3D images of selected SIS samples, scans of $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$: a) SIS PRISTINE, b) SIS + 1.5 % CHX, c) SIS + UV + 1.5 % CHX and d) SIS + PA + 1.5 % CHX.

Fig. 6. AFM 2D images of selected SBS samples, scans of $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$: a) SBS PRISTINE, b) SBS + 1.5 % CHX, c) SBS + UV + 1.5 % CHX and d) SBS + PA + 1.5 % CHX.

combining with CHX modification changed the structures of SBS and SIS copolymers. The FTIR analysis results for SIS and SBS polymers are presented in the following graphs (Figs. 8 and 9), with 8a and 8b illustrating SIS polymer modified with 0.5 % and 1.5 % CHX, respectively, and 9a and 9b showing SBS polymer modified with 0.5 % and 1.5 %

CHX, resp. Pristine SBS and SIS are coloured black for better comparison with the modifications. Pristine samples of both polymers showed characteristic peaks corresponding to the polystyrene (PS), polybutadiene (PB), and polyisoprene (PI) domains, which have been widely reported in the literature [38–41].

Fig. 7. AFM 3D images of selected SBS samples, scans of 50 × 50 μm: a) SBS PRISTINE, b) SBS + 1.5 % CHX, c) SBS + UV + 1.5 % CHX and d) SBS + PA + 1.5 % CHX.

Fig. 8. FTIR spectra of the SIS polymer with the addition of a) 0.5 % CHX, b) 1.5 % CHX.

Fig. 9. FTIR spectra of the SBS polymer with the addition of a) 0.5 % CHX, b) 1.5 % CHX.

The pristine SIS polymer shows a characteristic peak for each domain. The first peak visible at 3026 cm^{-1} is attributed to the aromatic C-H stretching vibrations on the benzene ring, confirming the presence of PS units [42]. The next two visible peaks at 2960 cm^{-1} and 2850 cm^{-1} are attributed to the aliphatic asymmetric ($-\text{CH}_3$) and symmetric ($-\text{CH}_2$) C-H stretching vibrations, respectively, the first confirmation of PI units. The peak at 1640 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C=C stretching vibrations of unsaturated isoprene units [40,43,44]. In addition, two peaks at 1450 cm^{-1} and 1375 cm^{-1} are observed, attributed to the aliphatic C-H bending vibrations corresponding to $-\text{CH}_2$ scissoring and $-\text{CH}_3$ symmetric bending, respectively, proving once again the presence of PI domains [42,43,45]. The final two peaks at 755 cm^{-1} and 696 cm^{-1} characterize the aromatic C-H bending (out-of-plane) vibrations of monosubstituted benzene, the final confirmation of the PS domain [41, 46].

The FTIR spectra of modified SIS polymer samples (Fig. 8a and b) show some changes after using individual modification techniques. The SIS samples with an addition of 0.5 % and 1.5 % CHX display two intensity peaks at 2916 and 2848 cm^{-1} attributed to C-H stretching in the alkyl chains of CHX [47]. The peak observed at 1541 cm^{-1} is associated with the N-H bending of amine groups in CHX [48]. Hydrogen bonding or interactions between CHX and the polymer matrix could create new peaks or modify existing ones without causing full oxidation. For example, the 1035 cm^{-1} peak could be related to C-N stretching resulting from such interactions [48,49]. In plasma-treated and UV-activated SIS samples, the main functional changes in the FTIR spectrum include the introduction of hydroxyl (O-H) and carbonyl (C=O) groups due to oxidation and the formation of ether or ester bonds between CHX and SIS. There are also contributions from aromatic C-H stretching and C=C stretching, indicating the presence of the aromatic rings of CHX and the styrene block in SIS [49,50]. In the SIS samples modified by plasma (PA), the peak appears at 1542 cm^{-1} , suggesting N-H bending from amine groups in CHX. Peaks in the range of 1481 to 1378 cm^{-1} are likely to correspond to the C-H bending from alkyl groups in CHX and SIS [48]. The alkyl chains of CHX and the C-H bending of the SIS polymer have shifted or changed in intensity due to interactions between CHX and the plasma-modified SIS surface. The next peak at 1314 cm^{-1} is probably due to the C-N stretching of the amine groups of CHX. Oxygen functional groups such as ethers typically show C-O stretching in the 1200 to 1300 cm^{-1} range, and the peak at 1249 cm^{-1} due to plasma treatment corresponds to this [48]. In UV-modified samples, the region of 3600 – 3250 cm^{-1} is also attributed to O-H stretching of hydroxyl groups introduced by UV activation, with a possible N-H stretching of CHX. The presence of aromatic rings of CHX is evidenced by the peak at 3023 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the aromatic C-H stretching. The next peak at 1714 cm^{-1} is probably the C=O stretching of oxidised SIS (likely carbonyl groups formed by UV activation). The C=C stretching of the aromatic moiety of CHX is associated with the peaks in the 1645 to 1532 cm^{-1} region with a contribution of N-H bending overlapping around 1540 cm^{-1} [51]. The region of 1492 – 1365 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C-H bending of alkyl groups in CHX and SIS polymer with their interactions. And the last area of peaks at 1250 to 1025 cm^{-1} is likely for the C-O stretching (from UV-induced modifications) with the contribution of C-H bending from CHX and interactions with the SIS matrix [47,51–54].

The pristine SBS polymer shows peaks characteristic of its domains. The first peak at 3004 cm^{-1} confirms the presence of the PB unit, corresponding to the aromatic C-H stretching vibrations of the CH groups in the aromatic ring. The next two peaks at 2915 and 2840 cm^{-1} are attributed to the aliphatic C-H stretching vibrations, specifically asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the CH_2 groups in the PB units, respectively [55–58]. The next two appearing peaks at 1493 and 1450 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the deformation vibrations of the CH_2 groups in *cis*-PB and *trans*-PB units, respectively. They can also be attributed to the aromatic C=C stretching vibrations of the carbons in the ring [57]. Another peak at 964 cm^{-1} is associated with the C-H

(out-of-plane) vibration of the CH groups near the double bond in *trans*-PB units. The last two peaks in this spectrum, at 746 and 697 cm^{-1} , confirm the presence of the PS unit and correspond to the aromatic C-H (out-of-plane) vibrations of monosubstituted benzene [57–61].

The FTIR spectra of modified SBS polymer samples (Fig. 9a–b) show some changes due to the specific technique. The trend of CHX incorporation is very similar to the SIS samples. In the SBS samples modified with 0.5 % and 1.5 % CHX, the two peaks appearing at 2915 and 2843 cm^{-1} are probably related to the aliphatic C-H stretching in CHX [47, 62]. This was also observed in the SIS-modified sample. The next peak appears at 1540 cm^{-1} and corresponds to the N-H bending of amine groups in CHX. Another peak at 1313 cm^{-1} is for the C-N stretching vibration of amine groups in CHX [48]. The most significant functional changes in the FTIR spectrum of SBS samples, which have also been activated by plasma or UV light, show similar results to the ones of modified SIS samples. In addition, the presence of the styrene block and the aromatic rings of CHX is demonstrated by the contributions of aromatic C-H stretching and C=C stretching in SBS. In the plasma-modified SBS samples, the N-H bending vibration of amine groups in CHX is visible at 1540 cm^{-1} . The region at 1401 – 1386 cm^{-1} represents the C-H bending of alkyl groups in CHX and SBS. These interactions cause the shift or change in intensity due to the interactions between the PA-modified SBS surface and CHX. The last peak at 1048 cm^{-1} is for the C-N stretching vibration from amine groups in CHX [48,50,63]. UV-modified SBS samples show O-H stretching vibrations from hydroxyl groups induced by UV activation with a possible contribution from N-H stretching of CHX in the range of 3600 – 3250 cm^{-1} . The first visible peak occurs at 3024 cm^{-1} and is related to the aromatic C-H stretching vibration of CHX [48]. The next peak at 1714 cm^{-1} is probably formed by the C=O stretching of carbonyl groups from oxidation of the SBS surface due to UV activation [48,63]. The region of peaks at 1639 – 1532 cm^{-1} is formed by the C=C stretching vibrations of the aromatic rings of CHX and also by the N-H bending vibrations [48,49,51,53]. The C-H asymmetric (1451 cm^{-1}) and symmetric (1375 cm^{-1}) bending vibrations from interactions of alkyl groups in CHX and from SBS polymer are also visible [48,55].

FTIR analysis of SIS and SBS polymers with specific modifications reveals changes in the structure of the polymers due to surface modifications (C-O and C=O stretching) and confirms that CHX is incorporated (N-H, C-N, C-H bending and stretching).

3.5. Antibacterial efficiency

The graphs below show the results of the antibacterial activity measurements on SIS (Fig. 10a, S4a) and SBS (Fig. 10b–S4b) samples (the S Figs., S4a and S4b for DTAB-modified samples are presented in Supplementary material). CHX-modified samples showed much better antibacterial activity than DTAB-modified samples. Therefore, the results for CHX-modified samples are presented in this manuscript and DTAB-modified ones in Supplementary. CHX interacts with polymer surfaces through electrostatic interactions. The cationic nature of chlorhexidine is attracted to negatively charged polymer surfaces [64–66]. CHX is effective against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* because it works in two ways as a highly effective cationic antimicrobial agent. Its strong attachment to an important number of negatively charged phospholipids greatly disrupts bacterial membranes. It can penetrate the cell wall of some Gram-positive bacteria, such as *S. aureus*, and destabilizes the outer membrane of several Gram-negative bacteria, including *E. coli* [67]. UV or plasma treatment improved the antibacterial effectiveness of the chlorhexidine samples, likely due to improved binding or surface adsorption of the antimicrobial agent. For example, SBS + UV + CHX 0.5 % achieved very good antibacterial efficiency, with 1.8 % of total bacterial survival. SIS + UV + CHX 0.5 % showed outstanding antibacterial effects, with bacterial survival only 0.2 %, making it the best among the samples tested. CHX and UV treatment together create highly antimicrobial surfaces, as these results show. DTAB-modified samples

Fig. 10. Dependence of number of colony forming units (CFU) for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* at a) SIS and b) SBS polymer films with CHX modifications and plasma (PA) and UV treatment at two different concentrations.

(Fig. S4a and S4b) showed significantly reduced effectiveness against both bacteria. These samples consistently displayed bacterial survival percentages above 30 %. CHX-treated samples showed better efficiency, particularly against *E. coli*. DTAB demonstrably interacts with a meaningful amount of *S. aureus*; however, its penetration of the importantly thick peptidoglycan layer is greatly lower than that of CHX, which possesses additional antibacterial properties beyond simple cationic disruption [68]. Under similar conditions, CHX is a more effective antimicrobial agent than DTAB. As shown in Table 1, the antibacterial performance of the CHX-modified SIS and SBS block copolymer samples prepared in this study demonstrates a significant improvement compared to several previously reported polymeric systems. The SIS samples exhibited antibacterial efficiencies in the range of 75–99 %, while the SBS samples reached up to 80–99 %, depending on both sample composition and bacterial colony. Given the relatively low concentrations of CHX used (0.5 and 1.5 %), these results are quite notable. In comparison, several systems reported in the literature required much higher concentrations of CHX to achieve moderate antibacterial effects [69–71]. Moreover, compared to more complex or

specific preparation techniques (e.g., UV-initiated polymerisation, layer-by-layer assembly, or remote plasma deposition), the solvent casting method used in this study is simple and more practical for potential applications, such as surface coatings on different substrates. In addition, the samples were tested against both Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria and showed strong antibacterial effects in both cases.

4. Conclusion

In this work, novel polymer films modified with two different antibacterial compounds (CHX and DTAB) were prepared as antibacterial surfaces for various applications. This study shows the potential of these selected cationic biocides as modifying agents used on SIS and SBS polymer films, and it shows their value as antibacterial coatings. The modifications induced by the UV light along with plasma surface treatment led to important enhancements of antimicrobial activity. Surface wettability and charge, in addition to adhesion properties on different substrates (glass, aluminium and surgical steel), were also

Table 1

Comparison of the antibacterial efficiency determined for our samples and the measured ones on different types of polymeric material and CHX concentrations by other authors.

Material	Used concentration of CHX (wt %)	Sample preparation method	Target	Antibacterial efficiency results	Reference
Nitrated acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS)	Not specified	Oscillated blending method	<i>E. coli</i> <i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial efficiency in the range of 30–98 % (depends on the sample and bacterial colony)	[64]
Chitosan/poly(acrylic acid) composite	0.006, 0.013, 0.025, 0.05, 2	Layer-by-layer assembly method	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial efficiency in the range of 18–22 % (depends on the sample)	[65]
Thermoplastic starch (TPS)	1, 5, 10, 20	Blending method	<i>E. coli</i> <i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial efficiency in the range of 60–70 % (depends on the sample and bacterial colony)	[69]
Epoxidized natural rubber (ENR)	0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10	Melt-blending and crosslinking methods	<i>E. coli</i> <i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial efficiency measurable only in one sample (70 %)	[70]
Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) nanocoatings	10	Remote plasma-assisted vacuum deposition	<i>E. coli</i>	Antibacterial efficiency in the range of 40–86 % (depends on the sample)	[71]
Polystyrene-block-polyisoprene-block-polystyrene (SIS)	0.5, 1.5	Solvent casting method	<i>E. coli</i> <i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial efficiency in the range of 75–99 % (depends on the sample and bacterial colony)	This study
Polystyrene-block-polybutadiene-block-polystyrene (SBS)	0.5, 1.5	Solvent casting method	<i>E. coli</i> <i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial efficiency in the range of 80–99 % (depends on the sample and bacterial colony)	This study

thoroughly improved. Films treated with CHX consistently exhibited better antibacterial performance among all tested modifications; the SIS + UV + CHX 0.5 % sample was the most effective, reducing bacterial survival to just 0.2 %. In contrast, DTAB-modified films displayed little antimicrobial activity, pointing out the great importance of molecular structure and binding effectiveness to bacterial inhibition. To evaluate the stability of the samples in an aqueous environment, a water uptake and swelling ratio test was conducted. The results revealed that all samples exhibited stability, with swelling ratio values below 5 %. According to surface characterization, UV and plasma treatments improved the polymer matrix's CHX retention and hydrophilicity through the addition of polar functional groups. AFM characterization revealed differences between the selected copolymers, particularly with regard to the roughness of the selected samples. The SBS polymer appeared rougher in all forms of modification. FTIR analysis revealed structural changes in SIS as well as SBS films and confirmed the successful incorporation of CHX. In cross-cut testing, all SBS-based films showed higher substrate adhesion than all SIS-based films, and SBS + UV + CHX 0.5 % also exhibited good adhesion to aluminium, glass and surgical steel. Therefore, SBS films could be a better option for antibacterial coatings on selected substrates. These are suitable for applications that require extraordinary durability and antimicrobial properties. These findings highlight all practical applications of both SIS and SBS antimicrobial coatings in the fields of healthcare, waste management, and food safety, as microbial contamination is a very major concern there. As we presented, a promising strategy for developing antimicrobial surfaces with significant antibacterial activity and strong adhesion to certain substrates is to combine UV or plasma activation with the incorporation of CHX. Even so, difficulties remain in improving adhesion for SIS-based coatings, guaranteeing antimicrobial stability lasts, and assessing biocompatibility and ecological effect. This study shows the development of antimicrobial polymer coatings based on block copolymers modified with selected cationic biocides. It also points out the superior performance of CHX over DTAB, in addition to the importance of surface modification techniques. With additional refinement, these materials could serve as quite effective antimicrobial surfaces for many applications, as well as improve hygiene and safety in all sorts of industries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kateřina Hamalová: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Viktorie Neubertová:** Validation, Investigation. **Aděla Jagerová:** Investigation. **Anna Kutová:** Investigation. **Jan Novotný:** Investigation. **Zdeňka Kolská:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used DeepL Write and QuillBot in order to check spelling and grammar and improve the fluency of the manuscript. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the assistance provided by a grant from the

Programme Johannes Amos Comenius under the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004558 Advanced MULTISCALE materials for key Enabling Technologies.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2025.109020>.

Data availability

The raw data required to reproduce the above results are available for download at: doi:10.5281/zenodo.15341108. Data will be available after the article is published.

References

- [1] Y. Yang, Z. Cai, Z. Huang, X. Tang, X. Zhang, Antimicrobial cationic polymers: from structural design to functional control, *Polym. J.* 50 (2018) 33–44, <https://doi.org/10.1038/pj.2017.72>.
- [2] A. Muñoz-Bonilla, M. Fernández-García, The roadmap of antimicrobial polymeric materials in macromolecular nanotechnology, *Eur. Polym. J.* 65 (2015) 46–62, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2015.01.030>.
- [3] J.A. Callow, M.E. Callow, Trends in the development of environmentally friendly fouling-resistant marine coatings, *Nat. Commun.* 2 (2011) 244, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms1251>.
- [4] Y. Jiao, L. Niu, S. Ma, J. Li, F.R. Tay, J. Chen, Quaternary ammonium-based biomedical materials: state-of-the-art, toxicological aspects and antimicrobial resistance, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 71 (2017) 53–90, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2017.03.001>.
- [5] D. Zubris, K. Miniole, W. Wuest, Polymeric Quaternary ammonium compounds: versatile antimicrobial materials, *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.* 17 (2016) 305–318, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568026616666160829155805>.
- [6] W. Ren, W. Cheng, G. Wang, Y. Liu, Developments in antimicrobial polymers, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A: Polym. Chem.* 55 (2017) 632–639, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pola.28446>.
- [7] M.S. Ganewatta, C. Tang, Controlling macromolecular structures towards effective antimicrobial polymers, *Polymer* 63 (2015) A1–A29, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2015.03.007>.
- [8] D. Druvari, N. Koromilas, V. Bekiari, G. Bokias, J. Kallitsis, Polymeric antimicrobial coatings based on Quaternary ammonium compounds, *Coatings* 8 (2017) 8, <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings8010008>.
- [9] H. Li, H. Bao, K.X. Bok, C.-Y. Lee, B. Li, M.T. Zin, L. Kang, High durability and low toxicity antimicrobial coatings fabricated by quaternary ammonium silane copolymers, *Biomater. Sci.* 4 (2016) 299–309, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5BM00353A>.
- [10] T. Wei, Z. Tang, Q. Yu, H. Chen, Smart antibacterial surfaces with switchable bacteria-killing and bacteria-releasing capabilities, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 9 (2017) 37511–37523, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b13565>.
- [11] Z.X. Voo, M. Khan, K. Narayanan, D. Seah, J.L. Hedrick, Y.Y. Yang, Antimicrobial/antifouling polycarbonate coatings: role of block copolymer architecture, *Macromolecules* 48 (2015) 1055–1064, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ma5022488>.
- [12] K. Rajkowska, A. Koziróg, A. Otlewska, M. Piotrowska, P. Nowicka-Krawczyk, B. Brycki, A. Kunicka-Styczynska, B. Gutarowska, Quaternary ammonium biocides as antimicrobial agents protecting historical wood and brick, *Acta Biochim. Pol.* 63 (2015), <https://doi.org/10.18388/abp.2015.1134>.
- [13] A.G. Grigoras, Natural and synthetic polymeric antimicrobials with quaternary ammonium moieties: a review, *Environ. Chem. Lett.* 19 (2021) 3009–3022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-021-01215-w>.
- [14] I. Sulaeva, U. Henniges, T. Rosenau, A. Potthast, Bacterial cellulose as a material for wound treatment: properties and modifications. A review, *Biotechnol. Adv.* 33 (2015) 1547–1571, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2015.07.009>.
- [15] D. Morais, R. Guedes, M. Lopes, Antimicrobial approaches for textiles: from research to market, *Materials* 9 (2016) 498, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma9060498>.
- [16] A.N. Vereshchagin, N.A. Frolov, K.S. Egorova, M.M. Seitkaliyeva, V.P. Ananikov, Quaternary ammonium compounds (QACs) and ionic liquids (ILs) as biocides: from simple antiseptics to tunable antimicrobials, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 22 (2021) 6793, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22136793>.
- [17] W.A. Arnold, A. Blum, J. Branyan, T.A. Bruton, C.C. Carignan, G. Cortopassi, S. Datta, J. DeWitt, A.-C. Doherty, R.U. Halden, H. Harari, E.M. Hartmann, T. C. Hrubec, S. Iyer, C.F. Kwiatkowski, J. LaPier, D. Li, L. Li, J.G. Muñiz Ortiz, A. Salamova, T. Schettler, R.P. Seguin, A. Soehl, R. Sutton, L. Xu, G. Zheng, Quaternary ammonium compounds: a chemical class of emerging concern, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 57 (2023) 7645–7665, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.2c08244>.
- [18] F. Bureš, Quaternary ammonium compounds: simple in structure, complex in application, *Top. Curr. Chem.* 377 (2019) 14, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41061-019-0239-2>.
- [19] J. Morante, A.M. Quispe, B. Ymaña, J. Moya-Salazar, N. Luque, G. Soza, M. Ramos Chirinos, M.J. Pons, Tolerance to disinfectants (chlorhexidine and isopropanol)

- and its association with antibiotic resistance in clinically-related *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, *Pathog. Glob. Health* 115 (2021) 53–60, <https://doi.org/10.1080/20477724.2020.1845479>.
- [20] Y. Suzuki, T. Ohsumi, T. Isono, R. Nagata, T. Hasegawa, S. Takenaka, Y. Terao, Y. Noiri, Effects of a sub-minimum inhibitory concentration of chlorhexidine gluconate on the development of *in vitro* multi-species biofilms, *Biofouling* 36 (2020) 146–158, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2020.1739271>.
- [21] O. Grytsai, C. Ronco, R. Benhida, Synthetic accesses to biguanide compounds, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.* 17 (2021) 1001–1040, <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjoc.17.82>.
- [22] D. Nečas, P. Klapeček, Gwyddion: an open-source software for SPM data analysis, *Open Phys.* 10 (2012) 181–188, <https://doi.org/10.2478/s11534-011-0096-2>.
- [23] S. Zheng, M. Bawazir, A. Dhall, H.-E. Kim, L. He, J. Heo, G. Hwang, Implication of surface properties, bacterial motility, and hydrodynamic conditions on bacterial surface sensing and their initial adhesion, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 9 (2021) 643722, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2021.643722>.
- [24] A.M. Saleque, MdN.A.S. Ivan, S. Ahmed, Y.H. Tsang, Light-trapping texture biohydrogel with anti-biofouling and antibacterial properties for efficient solar desalination, *Chem. Eng. J.* 458 (2023) 141430, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.141430>.
- [25] Y. Tu, H. Ren, Y. He, J. Ying, Y. Chen, Interaction between microorganisms and dental material surfaces: general concepts and research progress, *J. Oral Microbiol.* 15 (2023) 2196897, <https://doi.org/10.1080/20002297.2023.2196897>.
- [26] T. Masuda, S. Yoshizawa, A. Noguchi, Y. Kozuka, N. Isu, M. Takai, Superior antibacterial surfaces using hydrophilic, poly(MPC) and poly(mOEGMA) free chains of amphiphilic block copolymer for sustainable use, *Heliyon* 10 (2024) e26347, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e26347>.
- [27] Z. Xie, P. Zhang, Z. Zhang, C. Chen, X. Wang, The choice of antimicrobial polymers: hydrophilic or hydrophobic? *Chin. Chem. Lett.* 35 (2024) 109768, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccl.2024.109768>.
- [28] F. Khoerunnisa, M. Nurhayati, N.A.A. Annisa, S. Fatimah, N. Nashrah, H. Hendrawan, Y.-G. Ko, E.-P. Ng, P. Oparakassit, Effects of benzalkonium chloride contents on structures, properties, and ultrafiltration performances of chitosan-based nanocomposite membranes, *Membranes* 12 (2022) 268, <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes12030268>.
- [29] D.F. Alves, M.O. Pereira, S.P. Lopes, Co-immobilization of ciprofloxacin and chlorhexidine as a broad-spectrum antimicrobial dual-drug coating for poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC)-based endotracheal tubes, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 16 (2024) 16861–16879, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.4c01334>.
- [30] A.V. Murueva, A.E. Dudaev, E.I. Shishatskaya, F.D.E. Ghorabe, I.V. Nemtsev, A. V. Lukyanenko, T.G. Volova, Biodegradable polymer casting films for drug delivery and cell culture, *Giant* 19 (2024) 100314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giant.2024.100314>.
- [31] Y. Mansourpanah, K. Alizadeh, S.S. Madaeni, A. Rahimpour, H. Soltani Afarani, Using different surfactants for changing the properties of poly(piperazineamide) TFC nanofiltration membranes, *Desalination* 271 (2011) 169–177, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2010.12.026>.
- [32] P. Bhati, A. Srivastava, R. Ahuja, P. Chauhan, P. Vashisth, N. Bhatnagar, Physicochemical properties of UV-Irradiated, biaxially oriented PLA tubular scaffolds, *Polymers* 15 (2023) 1097, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15051097>.
- [33] X. Pei, Q. Wang, Ultraviolet irradiation induced changes in the surface of phenolphthalein poly(ether sulfone) film, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 253 (2007) 4550–4553, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2006.10.011>.
- [34] J. Tyczkowski, H. Kierzkowska-Pawlak, J. Sielski, I. Krawczyk-Klys, Low-temperature plasma modification of styrene-butadiene block copolymer surfaces for improved adhesion—A kinetic approach, *Polymers* 12 (2020) 935, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12040935>.
- [35] H. Kaczmarek, M. Nowicki, I. Vuković-Kwiatkowska, S. Nowakowska, Crosslinked blends of poly(lactic acid) and polyacrylates: AFM, DSC and XRD studies, *J. Polym. Res.* 20 (2013) 91, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10965-013-0091-y>.
- [36] N. Vourdas, A. Tserepi, A.G. Boudouvis, E. Gogolides, Plasma processing for polymeric microfluidics fabrication and surface modification: effect of superhydrophobic walls on electroosmotic flow, *Microelectron. Eng.* 85 (2008) 1124–1127, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mee.2007.12.032>.
- [37] M. Tountas, D.G. Georgiadou, A. Zeniou, K. Seintis, A. Soulati, E. Polydorou, S. Gardelis, A.M. Douvas, T. Speliotis, D. Tsikritzis, S. Kennou, M. Fakis, E. Gogolides, D. Tsoukalas, P. Argitis, M. Vasilopoulou, Plasma induced degradation and surface electronic structure modification of Poly(3-hexylthiophene) films, *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 149 (2018) 162–172, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polydegradstab.2017.12.010>.
- [38] L.B. Canto, G.L. Mantovani, E.R. deAzevedo, T.J. Bonagamba, E. Hage, L.A. Pessan, Molecular characterization of styrene-butadiene-styrene block copolymers (SBS) by GPC, NMR, and FTIR, *Polym. Bull.* 57 (2006) 513–524, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-006-0577-4>.
- [39] P. Zhang, J. He, X. Zhou, An FTIR standard addition method for quantification of bound styrene in its copolymers, *Polym. Test.* 27 (2008) 153–157, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2007.09.004>.
- [40] B.C. Smith, The infrared spectra of polymers IV: rubbers, *Spectroscopy* (2022) 8–12, <https://doi.org/10.56530/spectroscopy.mz6968v1>.
- [41] B.C. Smith, The infrared spectra of polymers III: hydrocarbon polymers, *Spectroscopy* (2021) 22–25, <https://doi.org/10.56530/spectroscopy.mh7872q7>.
- [42] M.M. Eissa, S.H. Botros, A.F. Moustafa, Effect of triblock copolymers on homogeneity, mechanical properties and swelling behavior of IIR/SBR rubber blends, *Polym. Bull.* 74 (2017) 393–412, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-016-1720-5>.
- [43] V. Arjunan, S. Subramanian, S. Mohan, Fourier transform infrared and raman spectral analysis of trans-1,4-polyisoprene, *Spectrochim. Acta Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 57 (2001) 2547–2554, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1386-1425\(01\)00426-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1386-1425(01)00426-7).
- [44] A. Umer, F. Liaqat, A. Mahmood, MoO₃ nanobelts embedded Polypyrrole/SIS copolymer blends for improved electro-mechanical dual applications, *Polymers* 12 (2020) 353, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12020353>.
- [45] S. Tiwari, M. Srivastava, D.S. Bag, Infrared and microwave radiation assisted self-healing property of exfoliated-graphene incorporated styrene-isoprene-styrene nanocomposites, *J. Polym. Mater.* 0 (2025) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.32604/jpm.2025.057322>.
- [46] X. Luo, Y. Feng, X. Su, Swelling behaviours of styrene-isoprene-styrene triblock copolymers in supercritical methane, *Plast. Rubber Compos.* 47 (2018) 365–372, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14658011.2018.1495393>.
- [47] S. Hosseini, M. Kassae, S.H. Elahi, B. Bolhari, A novel binary chlorhexidine-chitosan irrigant with high permeability, and long lasting synergic antibacterial effect, *Nanochem. Res.* 3 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.22036/ncr.2018.01.010>.
- [48] R.M. Silverstein, F.X. Webster, D.J. Kiemle, *Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds*, seventh ed., J. Wiley & sons, Hoboken (N.J.), 2005.
- [49] T. Rema, J.R. Lawrence, J.J. Dynes, A.P. Hitchcock, D.R. Korber, Microscopic and spectroscopic analyses of chlorhexidine tolerance in *Delftia acidovorans* biofilms, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 58 (2014) 5673–5686, <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02984-14>.
- [50] B. Priyadarshini, S. Selvan, K. Narayanan, A. Fawzy, Characterization of chlorhexidine-loaded calcium-hydroxide microparticles as a potential dental pulp-capping material, *Bioengineering* 4 (2017) 59, <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering4030059>.
- [51] M.E. Cortés, R.D. Sinisterra, M.J. Avila-Campos, N. Tortamano, R.G. Rocha, The chlorhexidine: beta-cyclodextrin inclusion compound: preparation, characterization and microbiological evaluation, *J. Inclusion Phenom. Macrocyclic Chem.* 40 (2001) 297–302, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1012788432106>.
- [52] K. Garala, P. Joshi, J. Patel, A. Ramkishan, M. Shah, Formulation and evaluation of periodontal in situ gel, *Int. J. Pharm. Invest.* 3 (2013) 29, <https://doi.org/10.4103/2230-973X.108961>.
- [53] A.M. Young, P.Y.J. Ng, U. Gbureck, S.N. Nazhat, J.E. Barralet, M.P. Hofmann, Characterization of chlorhexidine-releasing, fast-setting, brushite bone cements, *Acta Biomater.* 4 (2008) 1081–1088, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2007.12.009>.
- [54] R. Scaffaro, L. Settanni, E.F. Gulino, Release profiles of carvacrol or chlorhexidine of PLA/graphene nanoplatelets membranes prepared using electrospinning and solution blow spinning: a comparative study, *Molecules* 28 (2023) 1967, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28041967>.
- [55] H. Yu, X. Bai, G. Qian, H. Wei, X. Gong, J. Jin, Z. Li, Impact of ultraviolet radiation on the aging properties of SBS-modified asphalt binders, *Polymers* 11 (2019) 1111, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11071111>.
- [56] X. Hou, S. Lv, Z. Chen, F. Xiao, Applications of fourier transform infrared spectroscopy technologies on asphalt materials, *Measurement* 121 (2018) 304–316, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2018.03.001>.
- [57] S.B. Munteanu, C. Vasile, Spectral and thermal characterization of styrene-butadiene copolymers with different architectures, *J. Optoelectron. Adv. Mater.* 7 (2005) 3135–3148.
- [58] E. Serrano, A. Zubeldia, M. Larrañaga, P. Remiro, I. Mondragon, Effect of different thermal treatments on the self-assembled nanostructures of a styrene-butadiene-styrene star block copolymer, *Polym. Degrad. Stabil.* 83 (2004) 495–507, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polydegradstab.2003.08.009>.
- [59] L. Iancu, P. Ghioca, B. Spurcaci, R.M. Grigorescu, C.-A. Nicolae, R.A. Gabor, Maleinized linear styrene-butadiene block-copolymers, *Mater. Plast.* 2013 (n.d.) 137–140.
- [60] J.-F. Masson, L. Pelletier, P. Collins, Rapid FTIR method for quantification of styrene-butadiene type copolymers in bitumen, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 79 (2001) 1034–1041, [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628\(20010207\)79:6<1034::AID-APP60>3.0.CO;2-4](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628(20010207)79:6<1034::AID-APP60>3.0.CO;2-4).
- [61] G. Wu, S. Zeng, E. Ou, P. Yu, Y. Lu, W. Xu, Photoinitiator grafted styrene-butadiene-styrene triblock copolymer, *Mater. Sci. Eng., C* 30 (2010) 1030–1037, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2010.05.004>.
- [62] P. Suriyaamporn, N. Sahatsapan, P. Patrojansophon, P. Opanasopit, M. Kumpugdee-Vollrath, T. Ngawhirunpat, Optimization of in situ gel-forming chlorhexidine-encapsulated polymeric nanoparticles using design of experiment for periodontitis, *AAPS PharmSciTech* 24 (2023) 161, <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-023-02600-0>.
- [63] J. Shen, H. Xie, Q. Wang, X. Wu, J. Yang, C. Chen, Evaluation of the interaction of chlorhexidine and MDP and its effects on the durability of dentin bonding, *Dent. Mater.* 36 (2020) 1624–1634, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2020.10.006>.
- [64] R. Watson, M. Maxwell, S. Dunn, A. Brooks, L. Jiang, H.J. Hill, G. Williams, A. Kotowska, N.D. Nikoi, Z. Stamataki, M. Banzhaf, D. Scurr, J.A. Bryant, F. De Cogan, Development of biocide coated polymers and their antimicrobial efficacy, *Nano Sel* 4 (2023) 442–453, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nano.202300005>.
- [65] B. Savdenbekova, A. Seidulayeva, A. Sailau, Z. Bekissanova, D. Rakhmatullayeva, A. Jumagazyeva, Investigation of antibacterial coatings based on chitosan/polyacrylic acid/chlorhexidine for orthopedic implants, *ACS Polym. Au* 4 (2024) 498–511, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acspolymersau.4c00049>.
- [66] S. Tambunlertchai, S. Srisang, N. Nasongkla, Development of antimicrobial coating by layer-by-layer dip coating of chlorhexidine-loaded micelles, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Med.* 28 (2017) 90, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10856-017-5899-2>.
- [67] C. Waller, J.K. Marzinek, E. McBurnie, P.J. Bond, P.T.F. Williamson, S. Khalid, Impact on *S. aureus* and *E. coli* membranes of treatment with chlorhexidine and

- alcohol solutions: insights from molecular simulations and nuclear magnetic resonance, *J. Mol. Biol.* 435 (2023) 167953, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmb.2023.167953>.
- [68] A. Grigor'eva, A. Bardasheva, A. Tupitsyna, N. Amirkhanov, N. Tikunova, D. Pyshnyi, E. Ryabchikova, Changes in the ultrastructure of *Staphylococcus aureus* treated with cationic peptides and chlorhexidine, *Microorganisms* 8 (2020) 1991, <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8121991>.
- [69] N. Thajai, K. Jantanasakulwong, P. Rachtanapun, P. Jantrawut, K. Kiattipornpithak, T. Kanthiya, W. Punyodom, Effect of chlorhexidine gluconate on mechanical and anti-microbial properties of thermoplastic cassava starch, *Carbohydr. Polym.* 275 (2022) 118690, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2021.118690>.
- [70] T. Kanthiya, N. Thajai, T. Chaiyaso, P. Rachtanapun, S. Thanakkasaree, A. Kumar, S. Boonrasri, T. Kittikorn, Y. Phimolsiripol, N. Leksawasdi, N. Tanadchangsang, K. Jantanasakulwong, Enhancement in mechanical and antimicrobial properties of epoxidized natural rubber via reactive blending with chlorhexidine gluconate, *Sci. Rep.* 13 (2023) 9974, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-36962-z>.
- [71] A. Mora-Boza, F.J. Aparicio, M. Alcaire, C. López-Santos, J.P. Espinós, D. Torres-Lagares, A. Borrás, A. Barranco, Multifunctional antimicrobial chlorhexidine polymers by remote plasma assisted vacuum deposition, *Front. Chem. Sci. Eng.* 13 (2019) 330–339, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11705-019-1803-6>.